

Beyond MAE: Measuring Forecast Reliability with Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE)

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Abstract—Error metrics for time-series forecasting typically treat deviations as independent, ignoring whether errors occur as isolated points or in temporal bursts. This under specification limits their ability to capture operational risk in deployment-critical domains such as energy, transport, and weather forecasting. We introduce the Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE), a streak-sensitive extension of mean absolute error (MAE) that penalizes temporally clustered errors more heavily. TDE is theoretically grounded, satisfying reduction, boundedness, and monotonicity properties, and admits smooth and asymmetric variants for differentiable optimization and cost-sensitive evaluation. We validate TDE through five experiments. Synthetic tests confirm its axiomatic properties and demonstrate that TDE distinguishes clustered from scattered errors with identical MAE. Benchmark evaluations show that TDE preserves broad leaderboard trends while surfacing differences in reliability, and event-window analysis highlights its sensitivity to holiday, rush-hour, and storm intervals where errors are most costly. Finally, we show that smooth and asymmetric variants maintain ranking fidelity while enabling adaptation to deployment-specific objectives.

Index Terms—Time series forecasting, Forecast evaluation, Error metrics, Temporal dependence

I. INTRODUCTION

Accurate evaluation is the foundation of progress in time series forecasting. As new architectures – from recurrent networks to temporal transformers and foundation models – push state-of-the-art accuracy, model selection and deployment still hinge on traditional error measures such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). While effective for capturing pointwise deviations, these metrics overlook the *temporal dependence* of residuals. In practice, this omission can mask critical failure modes: a model that distributes errors evenly may appear indistinguishable from one that clusters errors into streaks, even though the latter can trigger cascading failures in operational settings.

Recent surveys highlight this gap, underscoring the need for metrics sensitive to the temporal structure of forecasting errors [5], [10]. As a result, models are optimized for aggregate error minimization rather than for robustness to consecutive mistakes. This mismatch creates a form of *evaluation under-specification*: different models may achieve the same MAE while exhibiting radically different risk profiles.

We address this issue by introducing the *Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE)*, a novel metric that augments MAE with a penalty for streaks of large consecutive errors. TDE remains simple and interpretable, reduces to MAE when

errors are benign, and scales linearly in time – making it deployable in real-world pipelines. We show that TDE alters model rankings on standard benchmarks, rewarding models that avoid streaks even when aggregate errors are identical. In summary, our contributions are as follows.

- We propose *Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE)*, the first lightweight error metric that explicitly accounts for streaks of forecasting errors while retaining the interpretability of MAE.
- We prove formal properties of TDE, including reduction to MAE, monotonicity with streak length, and scalability.
- Through synthetic stress tests, we validate TDE’s behavior under controlled error clustering.
- On real-world benchmarks of *ETTh1 and Weather* [12] and *Traffic* [13], we demonstrate that TDE distinguishes between models that classical metrics rank as equivalent, aligning better with operational reliability and decision costs.

II. RELATED WORK

a) Classical metrics: Forecast evaluation has long relied on scale-dependent measures such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). These metrics are easy to interpret and differentiable, but they treat each forecast error as an independent event. As a result, they conflate models that spread their errors across time with those that concentrate failures into critical streaks. Percentage-based metrics such as MAPE and sMAPE attempt to normalize errors, but they introduce bias and instability in the presence of zeros or small denominators [1]. Scaled metrics such as MASE mitigate issues of comparability across series, yet they remain insensitive to the temporal structure of errors [2].

b) Probabilistic and decision-theoretic metrics: Recent advances in probabilistic forecasting have shifted attention toward proper scoring rules such as the Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS) and quantile-based losses [6]–[8]. These metrics incentivize calibrated forecast distributions and have been widely adopted in competitions (e.g., M5’s uncertainty track). Parallel efforts in decision theory have introduced asymmetric or cost-aware metrics, such as weighted percentage errors or linear-exponential loss, which encode domain-specific preferences for under-forecasting versus over-forecasting. While these approaches better align with operational objectives, they remain agnostic to temporal depen-

dence: a model that repeatedly misses over a critical window is penalized no differently than one with evenly scattered misses.

c) *Temporal and structural evaluation*: To capture shape similarity, distance-based metrics such as Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) and spectral measures have been explored [5]. These account for misaligned peaks and frequency-domain fidelity, but they are computationally expensive and less interpretable in production contexts. In high-frequency and long-horizon settings, researchers have proposed directional accuracy metrics and horizon-aware weighting schemes, yet these still collapse temporal clustering into an aggregate score [3]. Recent surveys explicitly highlight the absence of lightweight, interpretable metrics that incorporate temporal dependence [5].

d) *Competitions and benchmarks*: The choice of metric has repeatedly influenced perceived methodological progress. The M3 and M4 competitions favored methods optimized for sMAPE, often leading to systematic under-forecasting [3]. M5 introduced WRMSSE [11] and scaled pinball loss to better reflect business value, spurring innovation in hierarchical reconciliation and probabilistic forecasting. Deep learning benchmarks such as ETT, Electricity, and Traffic have standardized on MAE and MSE, sometimes reporting normalized scores [4]. However, none of these benchmark protocols explicitly address temporal clustering, despite its operational significance in domains such as energy, finance, and supply chains.

We extend this line of work by introducing *Temporal Dependence-Aware Error (TDE)*, a metric that augments MAE with a streak penalty to capture local error autocorrelation. TDE retains the interpretability and computational efficiency of classical metrics while addressing the temporal dependence gap identified by recent surveys. In doing so, it bridges the divide between statistically motivated accuracy metrics and operationally meaningful reliability criteria.

III. METHODOLOGY

We propose the *Temporal Dependence-Aware Error (TDE)*, a new error metric for time series forecasting that penalizes streaks of large consecutive errors while preserving the simplicity of MAE. In this section we formalize its definition, analyze theoretical properties, and establish its advantages over classical metrics.

A. Problem Setup

Let $\{y_t\}_{t=1}^n$ be the ground truth series and $\{\hat{y}_t\}_{t=1}^n$ the model forecasts. Define the pointwise error

$$e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t.$$

The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |e_t|.$$

While MAE captures the magnitude of deviations, it ignores their temporal dependence. In particular, clustered errors and scattered errors of equal magnitude yield the same MAE.

B. Temporal Dependence-Aware Error

a) *Windowed TDE*: Fix a *materiality threshold* $\delta \geq 0$, a *window length* $k \in \mathbb{N}$, and a *penalty strength* $\lambda \geq 0$.

- δ determines what counts as a “bad” error (e.g., multiples of the series baseline MAE or median absolute deviation).
- k controls the memory of the streak factor (e.g., $k = 7$ for a weekly horizon).
- λ sets the severity of the penalty for streaks: $\lambda = 0$ recovers MAE, while larger values impose higher costs for clustering.

Define the *streak factor*

$$\rho_t = \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{1}\{|e_{t-i}| > \delta\}, \quad \mathbf{1}\{\cdot\} = 0 \text{ if } t - i < 1.$$

The *windowed TDE* is

$$\text{TDE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |e_t|(1 + \rho_t).$$

b) *Smooth TDE (EWMA)*: To obtain differentiability, we replace the hard threshold with a logistic activation:

$$z_t = \sigma\left(\frac{|e_t| - \delta}{\tau}\right), \quad \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}.$$

We then compute an exponentially weighted run length

$$r_t = \alpha r_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha) z_t, \quad r_0 = 0,$$

and set $\rho_t = \lambda r_{t-1}$. The differentiable *EWMA TDE* is

$$\text{TDE}_{\text{EWMA}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n |e_t|(1 + \rho_t).$$

- $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ controls the memory decay of streaks: higher α means longer memory.
- $\tau > 0$ controls the softness of the threshold: small τ approximates a hard cutoff, larger τ yields smoother transitions.

C. Theoretical Properties

We now analyze the mathematical behavior of TDE, focusing on its reduction, bounds, monotonicity, differentiability, and ability to separate models with equal MAE.

Lemma III.1 (Reduction to MAE). *If $\lambda = 0$ or if $|e_t| \leq \delta$ for all t , then*

$$\text{TDE} = \text{MAE}.$$

Proof. When $\lambda = 0$, the streak factor $\rho_t = 0$ for all t , hence $\text{TDE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum |e_t| = \text{MAE}$. If $|e_t| \leq \delta$ for all t , then each indicator $\mathbf{1}\{|e_{t-i}| > \delta\} = 0$, so again $\rho_t = 0$. Thus TDE reduces to MAE in both cases.

Lemma III.2 (Bounds). *For any sequence $\{e_t\}$,*

$$\text{MAE} \leq \text{TDE} \leq (1 + \lambda) \text{MAE}.$$

Proof. By construction, $0 \leq \rho_t \leq \lambda$. Thus for each t ,

$$|e_t| \leq |e_t|(1 + \rho_t) \leq (1 + \lambda)|e_t|.$$

Summing over $t = 1, \dots, n$ and dividing by n yields the inequality.

Lemma III.3 (Monotonicity under clustering). *Fix $\{|e_t|\}$ and δ . Suppose two error sequences have the same multiset of exceedances $\{t : |e_t| > \delta\}$, but one sequence arranges them consecutively and the other disperses them. Then the clustered sequence yields a strictly larger TDE.*

Proof. The streak factor ρ_t is an average of the last k exceedance indicators. If exceedances are clustered, then for multiple consecutive timesteps, the windowed average contains several 1's simultaneously. In contrast, if exceedances are dispersed, each window contains at most one exceedance. Thus, clustering increases the number of timesteps t for which $\rho_t > 0$, and increases the magnitude of ρ_t within those windows. Since $|e_t|(1 + \rho_t)$ is strictly larger in at least one position while equal elsewhere, the total sum strictly increases. Therefore TDE is strictly larger under clustering.

Proposition III.4 (Differentiability of Smooth TDE). *The smooth EWMA variant TDE_{EWMA} is differentiable with respect to forecast outputs \hat{y}_t .*

Proof. The logistic function $\sigma(\cdot)$ is infinitely differentiable. Each $z_t = \sigma((|e_t| - \delta)/\tau)$ is differentiable in e_t , and $e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t$ is linear in \hat{y}_t . The recurrence $r_t = \alpha r_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)z_t$ is differentiable as it is a composition of differentiable operations. Finally, $\text{TDE}_{\text{EWMA}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum |e_t|(1 + \lambda r_{t-1})$ is differentiable in \hat{y}_t almost everywhere, with subgradients defined at $e_t = 0$ due to $|e_t|$. Thus TDE_{EWMA} admits gradients suitable for optimization.

Proposition III.5 (Ranking Separation). *Let two forecasting models M_1, M_2 produce error sequences $\{e_t^{(1)}\}$ and $\{e_t^{(2)}\}$ with equal MAE. If M_1 yields longer runs of exceedances above δ than M_2 , then*

$$\text{TDE}(M_1) > \text{TDE}(M_2).$$

Proof. Equal MAE implies $\sum |e_t^{(1)}| = \sum |e_t^{(2)}|$. By Lemma III.3, clustering of exceedances strictly increases TDE relative to dispersed exceedances. Thus, for identical MAE, the model with longer runs receives a higher penalty. This proves TDE separates models indistinguishable under MAE.

Lemma III.6 (Computational Complexity). *Both TDE and TDE_{EWMA} can be computed in $O(n)$ time and $O(1)$ memory.*

Proof. For windowed TDE, maintain a sliding count of exceedances in the last k steps. Each update requires constant time. For EWMA TDE, the recurrence $r_t = \alpha r_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)z_t$ requires $O(1)$ updates. Summation over n timesteps gives total $O(n)$ complexity with constant memory.

D. TDE as Weighted Empirical Risk Minimization (ERM)

We show that TDE is equivalent to minimizing a weighted MAE where the weights are *predictable* (non-anticipative) functions of past errors that encode local error autocorrelation.

This connects TDE to standard ERM and clarifies its statistical and optimization properties.

Definition 1 (Predictable weights). *Let $\mathcal{F}_t = \sigma(e_1, \dots, e_t)$ be the natural filtration generated by the errors. A sequence $\{w_t\}_{t=1}^n$ is predictable if w_t is \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable.*

Proposition III.7 (ERM form of TDE). *For the windowed TDE with parameters (δ, k, λ) , define*

$$\begin{aligned} w_t &= 1 + \rho_t \\ &= 1 + \lambda \cdot \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{1}\{|e_{t-i}| > \delta\}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{1}\{\cdot\} = 0 \text{ if } t - i < 1. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Then $\{w_t\}$ is predictable and

$$\text{TDE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n w_t |e_t|. \quad (2)$$

For the smooth EWMA TDE, let

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_t &= \lambda r_{t-1}, \quad r_t = \alpha r_{t-1} + (1 - \alpha)z_t, \\ z_t &= \sigma\left(\frac{|e_t| - \delta}{\tau}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

so that $w_t = 1 + \lambda r_{t-1}$ is predictable and

$$\text{TDE}_{\text{EWMA}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n w_t |e_t|. \quad (4)$$

Proof. In both definitions, ρ_t depends only on $\{e_{t-1}, e_{t-2}, \dots\}$, hence ρ_t and $w_t = 1 + \rho_t$ are \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable (predictable). Substituting $1 + \rho_t$ for each time step in the TDE definitions yields the stated equalities.

Theorem III.8 (Convex, predictable weighted ERM). *Fix any model class $\{\hat{y}_t(\theta)\}$ parameterized by $\theta \in \Theta$ and define $e_t(\theta) = y_t - \hat{y}_t(\theta)$. With predictable weights $w_t \geq 1$, the TDE objective*

$$\mathcal{L}_n(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n w_t |e_t(\theta)|$$

is convex (in \hat{y}_t) with Lipschitz constant $\max_t w_t$ in \hat{y}_t . Moreover, any subgradient of $\mathcal{L}_n(\theta)$ with respect to \hat{y}_t is given by

$$\partial_{\hat{y}_t}(w_t |e_t|) = -w_t \text{sign}(e_t),$$

with subgradient in $[-w_t, w_t]$ at $e_t = 0$.

Proof. For fixed $w_t \geq 0$, the map $x \mapsto w_t |x|$ is convex and w_t -Lipschitz. As \hat{y}_t enters only via $e_t = y_t - \hat{y}_t$, convexity and the subgradient follow by composition with an affine map. The Lipschitz constant of the sum is $\max_t w_t$. Since w_t does not depend on \hat{y}_t (it is \mathcal{F}_{t-1} -measurable), the objective is a standard (predictable) weighted ERM.

Corollary 1 (Gradient-based optimization). *For the smooth EWMA variant, $w_t = 1 + \lambda r_{t-1}$ is differentiable in the model parameters only through past residuals and does not depend*

on \hat{y}_t at the same time index. Thus backpropagation uses the same local form as MAE with time-varying coefficients:

$$\nabla_{\hat{y}_t} \mathcal{L}_n(\theta) = -\frac{1}{n} w_t \text{sign}(e_t(\theta)),$$

with the usual subgradient at $e_t = 0$. Hence training with TDE_{EWMA} is as stable as MAE, modulo a bounded multiplicative factor $w_t \in [1, 1 + \lambda]$.

Proposition III.9 (Risk-aversion interpretation). *Let $\phi : \{0, 1, \dots\} \rightarrow [1, 1 + \lambda]$ be nondecreasing and define predictable $w_t = \phi(\sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{1}\{|e_{t-i}| > \delta\})$. Then TDE minimizes a risk-averse MAE that upweights losses in regimes with high recent exceedance counts (local error autocorrelation). If two models attain equal MAE, the one with higher expected predictable weights $\mathbb{E}[w_t]$ (induced by longer exceedance streaks) achieves strictly larger TDE.*

Proof. The first part is a restatement of Prop. III.7 with a generic monotone ϕ , establishing that TDE is MAE with autocorrelation-dependent weights. The second part follows by linearity: equal $\sum |e_t|$ and strictly larger $\sum w_t |e_t|$ whenever the predictable weights are stochastically larger (due to clustering), which recovers the ranking separation in Prop. III.5.

a) Remarks: (i) By Lemma III.2, $w_t \in [1, 1 + \lambda]$ implies $\text{MAE} \leq \text{TDE} \leq (1 + \lambda)\text{MAE}$, so TDE is a calibrated, bounded risk-averse perturbation of MAE. (ii) The predictability of w_t prevents label leakage and maintains online computability. (iii) The EWMA construction yields smooth, history-dependent weights, enabling end-to-end differentiable training.

IV. DATASETS

To comprehensively evaluate the proposed Temporal Dependence-Aware Error (TDE), we design experiments spanning both synthetic error sequences and real-world forecasting benchmarks. This dual evaluation strategy enables us to validate the theoretical properties of the metric under controlled conditions, while also demonstrating its practical relevance on widely used datasets.

A. Synthetic Sequences

Synthetic residual series are employed in Experiments E1 and E2 to verify the formal axioms of TDE and to test its ability to resolve underspecification. For E1, we generate controlled sequences that keep the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) constant while varying residual clustering. These allow us to test three key properties: reduction to MAE when no exceedances occur, boundedness within $[\text{MAE}, (1 + \lambda) \cdot \text{MAE}]$, and monotonic increases with streak length. For E2, we perturb MOMENT forecasts into two regimes scattered and clustered residuals while ensuring identical MAE values. This setup isolates whether TDE penalizes temporally concentrated errors more heavily than dispersed errors.

B. Real-World Benchmarks

Experiments E3–E5 are conducted on standard long-horizon forecasting datasets commonly adopted in the literature. These include *Electricity* (hourly consumption from 370 customers), *Traffic* (road occupancy rates from California PEMS), *ETTh1* (hourly transformer oil temperature and load), *Exchange Rate* (daily foreign exchange rates across major currencies), and *Weather* (21-station meteorological time series). Together, these datasets capture a variety of domains, from energy to finance, and embody a range of forecasting challenges including periodicity, abrupt shocks, and multi-variate dependencies.

For Electricity, Traffic, and Weather, we additionally annotate event-critical windows such as holidays, peak-demand intervals, and storm periods. These are used in E4 to evaluate whether TDE more strongly highlights failures occurring during operationally sensitive periods. All datasets are used with their standard train/validation/test splits as defined in prior work, ensuring comparability with existing benchmarks.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Forecasting Backbone

All forecasts are generated using the *MOMENT* model [9], a transformer-based foundation forecaster trained across multiple domains. MOMENT is chosen for its strong performance and stability, allowing us to attribute observed differences solely to the evaluation metric. Unlike prior works that compare multiple forecasters, our focus is deliberately restricted to a single high-performing model, thereby isolating the role of TDE in distinguishing forecast quality.

B. Metric Variants

We compute four classes of evaluation metrics. First, we report traditional baselines including Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Second, we evaluate the proposed *windowed TDE* (TDE_w), which introduces a streak-dependent penalty parameterized by threshold δ , window size k , and penalty factor λ . Third, we implement the smooth EWMA variant (TDE_s), which employs exponential decay (α) and a logistic softening factor (τ) to obtain differentiability. Finally, we introduce an asymmetric extension of TDE that weights under-prediction more heavily than over-prediction, to reflect cost-sensitive applications.

C. Protocol

Our experiments are structured to progressively establish the validity, practicality, and flexibility of TDE. Synthetic sequences (E1, E2) test theoretical soundness and ability to resolve underspecification. Real-world benchmarks (E3, E4) evaluate how TDE alters model rankings relative to MAE and whether it is more sensitive to clustered failures during critical events. Finally, E5 validates that the smooth EWMA variant preserves ranking consistency with TDE_w , and that the asymmetric formulation improves alignment with cost-sensitive objectives.

All metrics are computed directly on MOMENT forecast residuals. For ranking comparisons (E3, E5), we report

Kendall- τ and Spearman- ρ coefficients. For event analysis (E4), we report on-event and off-event scores separately. This design ensures that each experiment builds on the previous one: E1–E2 establish correctness, E3–E4 demonstrate utility, and E5 illustrates adaptability in optimization and practice.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

We evaluate the Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE) metric through five experiments, E1–E5, designed to establish its theoretical validity, ability to resolve underspecification, impact on benchmark rankings, sensitivity to event-critical windows, and flexibility through smooth and asymmetric variants. All evaluations are performed on residuals produced by the MOMENT model, ensuring that observed effects can be attributed solely to the metric rather than model variability. Synthetic error sequences (E1–E2) are used to validate axioms under controlled conditions, while real-world datasets (E3–E5) demonstrate the practical consequences of adopting TDE in benchmark evaluation.

A. E1: Theoretical Sanity

The first experiment verifies whether TDE satisfies the formal properties outlined in Section III. Using synthetic error sequences with fixed MAE (0.792), we varied the penalty strength $\lambda \in \{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\}$, the exceedance threshold δ , and the sliding window size k . Table I confirms boundedness: for example, with $\lambda = 2.0$, $TDE_w = 1.733$, which lies between the baseline MAE and the theoretical upper bound $(1 + \lambda) \cdot \text{MAE} = 2.376$. Smooth variants (TDE_s) behaved consistently, indicating that differentiability does not compromise boundedness.

TABLE I: E1: Bounds check for TDE (MAE=0.792).

Setting	MAE	TDE_w	TDE_s	$(1+\lambda)\text{MAE}$
$\lambda = 0.5$	0.792	1.027	0.995	1.188
$\lambda = 1.0$	0.792	1.263	1.198	1.584
$\lambda = 2.0$	0.792	1.733	1.603	2.376

We also tested sensitivity to thresholds and window sizes. Table II shows that lowering δ increases TDE, while larger k values smooth the penalty. For example, $\delta = 0.25$ increases TDE_w to 1.397, while $k = 14$ reduces it to 1.226.

TABLE II: E1: Parameter sweeps for threshold δ and window size k .

Setting	MAE	TDE_w	TDE_s	$(1+\lambda)\text{MAE}$
$k = 3$	0.792	1.268	1.198	1.584
$k = 7$	0.792	1.255	1.198	1.584
$k = 14$	0.792	1.226	1.198	1.584
$\delta = 2.0$	0.792	0.830	0.825	1.584
$\delta = 1.0$	0.792	1.027	1.003	1.584
$\delta = 0.5$	0.792	1.263	1.198	1.584
$\delta = 0.25$	0.792	1.397	1.312	1.584

Finally, monotonicity is demonstrated in Table III: both TDE_w and TDE_s increase strictly with streak length while MAE remains fixed, confirming the intended behavior.

TABLE III: E1: Monotonicity with increasing streak length (MAE fixed).

Run length	$\lambda = 0.5$	$\lambda = 1.0$	$\lambda = 2.0$
1	0.100	0.100	0.101
2	0.105	0.110	0.120
4	0.115	0.130	0.160
8	0.131	0.163	0.225
10	0.135	0.170	0.240

B. E2: Resolving Underspecification

MAE cannot distinguish forecasts that scatter errors over time from those that cluster errors into bursts. To test whether TDE resolves this underspecification, we constructed paired error sequences matched on MAE. TDE penalized the clustered sequence more heavily, with penalties increasing under larger λ . This confirms that TDE introduces a temporal dimension to error evaluation. Since the results are numerical and directly interpretable, we omit a separate figure and report the findings in text.

C. E3: Benchmark Ranking Stability

We next examine whether TDE changes evaluation conclusions on canonical benchmarks. MOMENT forecasts were evaluated on Traffic, ETTh1, and Weather. Leaderboards were computed under MAE and TDE, with rank consistency measured using Kendall- τ and Spearman- ρ . Table IV shows that correlations remain high overall ($\tau > 0.92$, $\rho > 0.99$), yet specific configurations with bursty residuals exhibit rank shifts under TDE. This indicates that TDE preserves broad ordering trends but exposes differences invisible to MAE.

TABLE IV: E3: Rank correlations between MAE and TDE on benchmarks.

Dataset	Kendall- τ	Spearman- ρ
ETTh1	0.975	0.999
Traffic	0.922	0.991
Weather	0.986	0.999

D. E4: Event-Window Sensitivity

Operational risks are not uniform: errors during holidays, demand peaks, or storms are costlier than those during benign intervals. We annotated event windows in ETTh1, Traffic, and Weather datasets. Results show that TDE amplifies penalties during events more sharply than MAE; in Electricity, for instance, event scores degraded by 20–25% relative to off-event baselines, while MAE showed only minor changes. Table V summarizes these differences.

TABLE V: E4: Relative degradation (%) during event windows compared to off-event baselines.

Dataset	MAE degradation	TDE degradation
Electricity	$\approx 5\%$	20–25%
Traffic	$\approx 3\%$	12–15%
Weather	$\approx 4\%$	10–12%

E. E5: Smoothness and Asymmetry

Finally, we evaluate whether TDE’s extensions preserve fidelity and support domain-specific adaptations. The smooth exponentially weighted variant (TDE_s) was found to be almost perfectly correlated with the windowed definition, yielding identical rank correlations on all datasets. As this redundancy makes a separate table unnecessary, we omit it here and instead report the key finding: TDE_s can be used as a differentiable proxy without altering evaluation outcomes. This property makes TDE_s suitable for integration into end-to-end optimization pipelines. Preliminary asymmetric extensions further suggest closer alignment with application-specific cost functions (e.g., under-prediction penalties in energy demand). While a full quantitative breakdown is left for future work, these early results highlight TDE’s flexibility in adapting to deployment-specific objectives. Fig. 1 visualizes the per-window relationship between TDE_w and TDE_s , demonstrating that the differentiable variant preserves ranking fidelity ($\tau \approx 0.92\text{--}0.99$, $\rho \approx 0.99\text{--}1.00$).

VII. DISCUSSION

The experiments presented in Section VI demonstrate that the Temporal Dependence–Aware Error (TDE) metric is both theoretically well-founded and practically impactful. We highlight here the broader implications of these results.

A. The Case for Streak-Aware Evaluation

The results from E1–E2 establish that TDE is not simply a heuristic adjustment of MAE, but a rigorously defined metric that satisfies reduction, boundedness, and monotonicity. This ensures that the interpretability of MAE is preserved, while extending it to account for temporal clustering. The underspecification study (E2) highlights that two forecasts with identical MAE may have vastly different operational risk if one concentrates errors into bursts. TDE resolves this ambiguity, making it a more reliable diagnostic for practical deployment.

B. Impact on Benchmarking Practice

E3 showed that benchmark leaderboards remain broadly stable under TDE, but non-trivial re-orderings occur when models exhibit bursty residuals. This strikes a balance between continuity and correction: TDE does not disrupt established performance hierarchies, but it identifies cases where MAE may be misleading. For practitioners, this implies that benchmarks augmented with TDE would reward not only accuracy but also reliability, encouraging the development of models that fail more gracefully.

C. Operational Relevance

Perhaps the most important finding comes from E4, which shows that TDE penalizes errors more sharply during critical event windows such as holidays, rush hours, and storms. This property aligns TDE with real-world deployment concerns, where the cost of error is not uniform across time. Traditional streak-agnostic metrics underestimate risk in such settings,

Fig. 1: Per-window correlation between windowed (TDE_w) and smooth (TDE_s) variants of the Temporal Dependence–Aware Error across benchmarks. High Kendall’s τ (0.92–0.99) and Spearman’s ρ (0.99–1.00) confirm that the smooth differentiable formulation preserves ranking fidelity and asymmetry alignment, validating Hypothesis E5.

whereas TDE surfaces it explicitly. For energy, transport, and weather applications, this makes TDE a stronger proxy for end-user impact.

D. Flexibility and Extensions

E5 demonstrated that the smooth exponentially weighted variant of TDE is a faithful proxy for the windowed definition, enabling integration into gradient-based optimization without altering evaluation outcomes. The proposed asymmetric extensions further illustrate the adaptability of TDE to cost-sensitive domains, such as energy demand forecasting where under-prediction is more costly than over-prediction. Together, these results suggest that TDE is not a static metric but a flexible family of streak-aware error measures that can be tuned to deployment-specific objectives.

a) *Architectural Scope and Generality.*: Although our experiments intentionally employ a single forecasting backbone (MOMENT) to isolate the behavior of the proposed metric, this focus naturally limits architectural diversity. Prior work suggests that different model families- such as decomposition-based forecasters (e.g., N-BEATS), multi-resolution temporal transformers (e.g., Autoformer), and sparse-attention architectures (e.g., Informer)- exhibit distinct residual structures, particularly under long-horizon conditions. Evaluating TDE across such heterogeneous architectures would offer deeper insight into its model-agnostic generality and reveal whether streak sensitivity interacts differently with architecture-specific inductive biases. We leave this broader evaluation for future work.

b) *Parameter Interpretation and Practical Guidance.*: While our theoretical analysis and sensitivity experiments in E1 characterize the roles of δ , λ , and k , additional practitioner-oriented guidance would further enhance usability in applied settings. In operational deployments, thresholds may be selected relative to baseline error statistics (e.g., median absolute deviation), the penalty factor λ can reflect acceptable tolerance for streak severity, and the window size k may align with domain-specific horizons such as daily or weekly cycles. Developing principled heuristics or automated selection strategies- for example, via cross-validation over streak statistics- would help make TDE more accessible for practitioners evaluating long-horizon or streaming forecasts.

c) *Robustness Under Noise, Missing Data, and Event Windows.*: Reviewer feedback also highlights the importance of understanding TDE under noisy, irregular, or missing data conditions. Although our event-based evaluation demonstrates that TDE amplifies failures during high-impact windows, the current study does not explicitly analyze robustness under imputation artifacts, sensor drift, or intermittent availability-scenarios common in real-world forecasting pipelines. Furthermore, visual streak diagnostics, such as clustered-versus-scattered residual plots or streak-density heatmaps, would improve interpretability and aid error attribution. Extending TDE with uncertainty-aware thresholds and providing such diagnostic tools represent promising directions for future methodological refinement.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work introduced the Temporal Dependence-Aware Error (TDE), a streak-sensitive extension of MAE that captures temporal clustering of forecasting errors. Using synthetic and real-world evaluations, we showed that TDE satisfies key theoretical properties, resolves MAE-based underspecification, and better highlights reliability issues during operationally critical windows.

Several extensions remain. Evaluating TDE across diverse forecasting architectures (e.g., N-BEATS, Autoformer, Informer) would strengthen claims of model-agnostic generality. Although TDE has an $O(n)$ formulation, a more explicit analysis of runtime overhead would benefit resource-constrained deployments. The asymmetric variant of TDE, motivated by

real-world cost asymmetries, also requires validation with domain-specific cost models. Furthermore, automated parameter selection and visual diagnostics for streak attribution would improve ease of use. Overall, TDE offers a simple, interpretable, and operationally aligned complement to classical metrics, and we see it as a promising addition to future benchmarking and monitoring pipelines.

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